

Social Capital; Case of Stakeholder Approach in Cimaragas Village

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ABSTRACT: This article examines the community of Cimaragas Village and the role of stakeholders in efforts to maintain social capital in Chiamis District, Cimaragas District, and Cimaragas Village. The data used in this study are primary and secondary data. The procedures performed were a literature review, in-depth interviews, and FGD (focus group discussion) methods/structured questionnaires. Next, the data analysis model used to test the hypotheses in this study is a prospective analysis approach using the MACTOR analysis tool. The result show converging power of actors that strengthen the process of dealing with COVID19 will strengthen the process of dealing with COVID19 and vice versa.

KEYWORDS: COVID19, Cimaragas Village; Social Capital.

1. INTRODUCTION

Society is driven by government so that the social costs of individual actions can be overcome. On the other hand, the basic facts show that the COVID-19 disruption has led to changes in social attitudes, social stratification, and social classes. This effect tends to reduce the ability to meet social costs, but this only occurs in some communities. (Maxlegs, 2020). Dependence on individual social costs can be overcome by harnessing the quality of social capital in society. Salman et al. (2021), in his study of duck herding social capital during the COVID-19 pandemic in South Sulawesi, found that his combination of three types of social capital—attachment, bridging, and social connection—is important in management. has shown to play an important role. pandemic vulnerability. Duck Breeder selectively combines her three elements of bonding, bridging, depending on the interests behind her interactions with various actors. The bridging and connecting role that social capital plays in interacting with farmers and irrigators is carried out to gain access to natural capital (rice fields and irrigation water). capital. (cash and loans).

According to Regus (2020), it's easy to see the emergence of social networks and volunteers during COVID-19, in the midst of a pandemic. The community has demonstrated a high level of resilience in protecting the community. Roommate supports communities affected by COVID-19. They promote social solidarity and allow residents to donate everything for emergency aid. In many initiatives, each community is built from the smallest unit. Take constructive measures in villages, including a sense of mutual responsibility for the common good (Zahrotunnimah, 2020).

Starting with understanding the importance of social capital in coping with the Covid-19 pandemic, this research is interested in examining the state of social capital in the Covid-19 era. Unlike other studies, the researchers are based on rural community stakeholders in the context of the Covid-19 pandemic. Social capital as defined by Coleman (1990). Lin (2001), Putnam (2000), and Rothstein (2003) are resources embedded in social networks, so active stakeholder relationships are very beneficial to the community. They offer reputational advantages, build trust, reduce transaction costs, and ensure smooth collaboration (Ojala and Luoma-aho, 2008).

Given the breadth of Indonesia's rural social networks, this study was limited to villages in Ciamis province, bearing in mind that this district, like other districts, has been affected by the virus-19 pandemic. West Java COVID-19 Case Statistics Dashboard Report (<https://dashboard.jabarprov.go.id/> 22 May 2022), West Java recorded 1,110,897 positive cases, of which 15,863 died and 1,092,317 recovered. Meanwhile, Ciamis province recorded 16,718 positive cases, of which 442 died and 16,276 recovered. The low number of Covid-19 cases suggests that social capital is still strong in the district.

Given the range of villages in the Ciamis Regency, this study confines himself to the village of Cimaragas in the Cimaragas District. The rationale is that the village is still within the reach of researchers, both in terms of time, money and other resources. Preliminary surveys of the area also show that settlements are characterized by strong social relationships among residents, and they also face problems of social constraints.

Several social capital studies, such as that conducted by (Salman et al., 2021), have investigated social capital in duck grazing communities during the pandemic in South Sulawesi. (Olives et al., 2021) then examine the role of social capital in pandemic

response and recovery and the need to promote social cohesion to resolve tensions between groups. (Regus, 2020) considers the importance of activating social capital, a strategic tool for dealing with the pandemic situation. Some of these studies illustrate the importance of the role of social capital in pandemic situations. However, the role of stakeholders as actors sustaining the spread of the pandemic was not further explored.

A fundamental difference from previous studies is that this study highlights the role and influence of stakeholders in controlling the spread of COVID19. This study is novel regarding the use of an analytical tool, the MACTOR analysis based on actor influence. A tool for analyzing the relative strengths of actors or interest groups, the MACTOR analysis aims to enable us to examine the similarities and differences between various problems and goals to be achieved. . Using this tool, the authors attempt to provide overviews and policy recommendations, focusing on each stakeholder.

2. METHOD

The procedures performed were a literature review, in-depth interviews, and FGD (focus group discussion) methods/structured questionnaires. In addition, we obtained data from institutions associated with this study.

3. RESULT & DISCUSSION

According Emerging trends cannot be separated from the influence of institutional roles that play a key role in social activity. As a formal institution of quality in promoting action or social action. Clear and formal rules are a means to provide synergies and complementarities between public and civil institutions. Given that the spread of COVID-19 in Indonesia tends to increase, it causes deaths and losses in social, economic and social dimensions. The government issued his 2020 Executive Order No. 07 on Task Force to Accelerate Response to COVID-19. This aims to provide a basic principle for regional governments and between ministries/agencies to provide synergistic, fast, precise, focused and integrated steps. From this basis the Ciamis district government issued Decree number 433.2/kpts.166-illk/2020 concerning the task force for accelerating the handling of COVID-19 in Ciamis Regency which determined to form a task force for accelerating handling of COVID-19 with the aim of increasing regional resilience in the health sector, synergizing regional apparatuses in making policies with related stakeholders, anticipating escalation and preparedness of capabilities in preventing, detecting and responding to the spread of COVID19.

Apart from that, in order to follow up on the acceleration of the handling of COVID19, the Ciamis Regency government also issued instructions to the regent to organize PSSB as an effective step in accelerating the handling of COVID19. This activity certainly has an effective impact on the residents of the Cimaragas sub-district, report by puskesmas Cimaragas shows that Cimaragas Village is in the green zone which indicates that the handling of COVID19 in the Cimaragas area was successful.

The role of institutions has been described specifically in overcoming the spread of COVID-19 when it is linked to the social capital of institutions as stakeholder actors having the same function in overcoming the spread of COVID-19. According to Freeman and Mcvea (2008), a stakeholder is a group or individual that influences or can be influenced to achieve an organization's goals.

Based on this, the Cimaragas district manager said: A page with stakeholders such as TNI, POLRI, academics, medical services, the private sector, and the general public volunteering to help stop the spread of his Covid19 in the Cimaragas subdistrict. This declaration shows that the value of trust, an element of social capital, will continue to be pursued to overcome Covid 19. Actors will be reinforced through social media or through intensive weekly meetings. Through their respective activities, such as testing by TNI and Polsek, they are taking the initiative to shareholder initiatives, along with Karang Taruna, to identify those infected and provide masks to prevent COVID19. That's not all. The researcher is also involved in coping with COVID-19 by providing community her guidance through Billboard media as an educational step for the community to prevent her from COVID-19. In addition, since elementary and junior high school students learn through online media, they can avoid close contact. After that, the Department of Health carried out vaccination activities in the villages of Cimaragas district together with the village chiefs. Trust and norms are important social capital factors in maintaining the functioning of social capital, but normative factors cannot be separated when it comes to the sustainability of social capital. Based on interviews with researchers in identifying stakeholders involved in addressing Covid19, several parties were directly involved, including:

Village Government, UPTD Cimaragas District Health Center, Cimaragas Police, Karang Taruna, Principal, Community. The actor conveyed the goals that arose during the editing process: Facilities Procurement, Services, Community Empowerment, Community Development, Partnerships, Regulation, Security and Order. This is the goal of those involved in dealing with the

pandemic. If the object is part of the parameters of social capital: trust, networks, norms. The results of the surveys conducted by the researchers were correlated and informed the data entry process for the analysis tools. The impact and dependencies of stakeholders in dealing with COVID19 near the village of Cimaragas can be mapped into four quadrants.

Figure 1. Map of the distribution of influence and dependency on actors

It is found in the map of the distribution of influence and dependency on actors that it can be seen that Mal (local community) is in quadrant III which indicates that the dominated actors have low influence and high dependency. Then there are the PD (Village Government) as relay actors who have high influence and high dependency, including in quadrant II, who are actors who are key figures because they have high influence on the policies to be implemented. Furthermore, there are Puskesmas, Ak (Academics), KT (Karang Taruna), and Polsek as the dominant actors in the distribution map in quadrant I which indicates that these actors are supporters in policy making. The MDII competitiveness scale shows that there is positive feedback by actors in the objective of providing facilities, services, empowerment, community development, partnerships, regulations, security and order. However, there is a negative feedback from youth groups who think that regulatory objectives have deficiencies in the implementation process.

Figure 2. Histogram The MDII competitiveness

The histogram image shows the highest level of competition between stakeholders, indicating that youth organizations have the highest level of competition between stakeholders. Next, we hunt for young actors by tracking actors with acting level 1.1 in health centers. Next comes Polsek at competition level 1 and Village Hall at level 0.9. Academic is his second-to-last player with a competitive level of 0.9 and is in last position in the community.

Figure 3. Convergence between actors

The image above shows a strong relationship of convergence between actors. This is being addressed through very close ties between village governments, academics, community health centers and police in Cimaragas district. Interestingly, the private sector representative, Karang Taruna, maintains close ties with the village government, academics, community health centers and the Cimaragas Sector Police. However, it has weak convergence into society.

3. CONCLUSION

This article analysis shows that social capital for stakeholders plays an important role as a catalyst to empower actors to deal with the spread of COVID-19. This was done by the Village Government, Polsek, Puskesmas, academics in response to pandemic cases, Karang Taruna, and local communities. Where the village hall acts as a go-between and other actors become supporters of his fight against COVID19. Normative factors are one of the driving forces that encourage volunteers to help her fight the spread of COVID19.. From the private sector where a trader in Cimaragas sub-district provides donations to her COVID-19 infected residents, there is a strong empathy and motivation for mutual cooperation ingrained in the Cimaragas region, making the village of Cimaragas more agile and responsive. Covid-19 stakeholder role impact determinations can be read in detail from the results of the discussion. This explains how stakeholder convergence generates large influence and dependence when each actor has a strong influence on the desired goal. The strength of convergence in Village Government, Polsek, Puskesmas, Academics and Karang Taruna indicates a high degree of convergence, while Karang Taruna indicates weak convergence in local communities and youth organizations are involved in pandemic management. does not imply Separately, we show that the stronger the convergence of actors, the stronger the response to COVID-19 and vice versa.

AUTHORS' CONTRIBUTIONS

The title "AUTHORS' CONTRIBUTIONS" should be in all caps.

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